

Arts

HARNESSING IN INDIAN CONTEMPORARY ART AND INDIAN MEDIA MARKET: THE FUTURE POSSIBILITIES

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Abstract

In primitive times, humans first created sketches in caves with coal. The development of time introduced man's colours and gradually begun to wind up the shades of nature even in colours. Then gradually the chemical colours (substance colours) were used for painting. Alongside every one of these advancements, the artist has not abstained from illustration on the PC while changing himself after some time. The world of art and artist is extremely bizarre and stranger. There is also attraction and fear in this world and there is always a neglected place for this world. In contemporary times when the person has reached the moon, the development of technology has reduced the whole world Ground Flood has brought the whole world to a stage of art And consumerism and marketism have pulled out the art and made a big canvas, Then this is the right time, when a person evaluates how the thinking of the common man and the artist has changed over the art.

The commercialization of art is posing a threat. The artist is from middle-class society, which starts working from the beginning to improve its economic condition, influenced by the market. Some artists are destroyed in such a situation, some save themselves, who save themselves, they give something to art. The craft of craftsmanship isn't awful, it is awful to be impacted by the market. The art of the market is growing fast in contemporary times and in the same way, the art market is fast becoming a thing. Naturally, now art has started declaring the object of market value and in this way the meaning of art is changing rapidly. And the meaning of his originality is also changing. At this time, it is very difficult to differentiate between genuine or real and fake in painting in the contemporary art market. And counterfeit paintings are also being sold in the market.

Keywords: Contemporary Art; Media; Market.

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1. Introduction

The market of contemporary art has developed quite a lot today. The reason is that since specialists progressed toward becoming artists, artists gave it a market look. There are two types of artists

now. One, those who see art as a business, others who consider art as their duty. There are many artists Who do not make more than four or five pieces of work in a year and there are many such artists also who are making a piece of work every day. But there is a lot of difference between the two actors and their art also. If the art becomes professional, then there will be no concern in the society. Now society will not be concerned with art, then the artist also just starts paying attention and publicity.

Only due to people in the art market who have patience, the art market is also patiently moving forward towards development. There was a time when no one even asked the art market. But today the demand for art market has started to grow. When someone stepped into this area, difficulties were there in front of them. In the initial times, there art did not find any specific place. However, if they patiently evaluate their work or rely on their work, then all difficulties will be overcome. Sooner or later result of their patience, they will started to be recognized as an artist in the art market.

2. Indian Media Market

Indian society has a very wide tradition of art and culture. But if we look today, we have a sense of concern and apathy in Indian society with regard to modern or contemporary art. Even the traditional and folk arts have the same sentiment. On the other hand, investment in art or partnership has become a symbol of social and prestige for rich and influential people. In spite of doing a lot of good work, the artist's work does not sell, because the artist can't even admire him or his marketing only when he feels the need of art market. But behind the current ups and downs of the art market, the hands of big corporates are considered hands. As a result, India has started seeing art as a business.

The market of the art is growing fast in contemporary times and in the same way, the art market is fast becoming a thing. Naturally, now art has started declaring the object of market value and in this way the meaning of art is changing rapidly. And the meaning of his originality is also changing. At this time, it is very difficult to differentiate between real and fake in painting in the contemporary art market. And counterfeit paintings are also being sold

It was sometimes said that art provides human education, cultured, rituals but since the market has been dominated by art, prices have started to dissipate rapidly. By keeping law and order and limitations in mind, the only art of art is becoming like money. This is the reason that the trend of copying art has increased. Today, in the art market, 25 to 30 percent of fake artworks are being sold as real. This is a new discipline of art in which nobody cares about the rules and regulations.

Now, talking about the Indian art market, we find that in the last few years, auction houses organized by indigenous and foreign entities have begun to keep good and historically important artwork composed by Indian established artists in their collections. They consider these artifacts as "real assets" like sleeping, which is a safe capital during the economic downturn. Because artifacts are also considered to be a way of investment compared to other investments. There is not much difference between the artists' artifacts, but the investment is considered safe. New artists' artifacts show a lot of difference in price, but after a long time, more profit can be expected.

Talking about the change in art, it is necessary to mention this naturalness that we cannot live for a long time in a harmonious environment following our traditional art styles. When we changed our apparel, changed lives, changed interests, physical pleasures - changed facilities and music - there was a lot to change in literature, but definitely to change visual arts. But today also the crisis is in front of us that we did not 'see' this change. We left behind somewhere.

Even today we see more references from art. If we go to Khajuraho, Elephanta, Ajanta, Bhaa, Konark or other temples - in caves or go to art galleries and museums, then we see artists linking them with references. We have got a habit of seeing a reference to know a story with every masterpiece. Contextualities on creativity are heavier. If a monkey is flying with mud and mountain, then it is 'Hanumanji' And seeing them, you should close your eyes by adding hand. The need to see that picture or idol's creativity or art ends there right there. We cannot see anything ahead of it Peacock pans and flutes are seen in any picture or idol, then the eyes should be closed by adding hand to 'Lord Krishna'. His art, his structure, his composure, the media and the technical possibilities of his beauty etc. all becomes subdued in front of the context.

It is also a problem of art today which can be seen not only in the works of religious, mythological references but in 'contemporary' art. The seller wants to know his details. So that he can make a masterpiece important by making a buyer a story, a reference, and earn more money. The audience also wants to hear it. The result was that today the artist becomes less engaged in creating details and less context for his composition and gathering references. Sometimes the point of view of crafts is due to weak work. And the reason for the meeting of the booklets and artists is made.

3. Conclusion

In any country, the art market can only be developed when there is a constant development of the cultural consciousness of the society, which is a long and continuous process. During the 21st Century in China, art education system, construction of public museums and heart of the young artists was spent. In the same way, in India today, the need for encouraging basic development for the art market is being felt. For this, it is necessary today that big industrialists and real estate companies join the arts and play their part in the events

Today, more and more government support is needed to promote contemporary art in India. So far in India the private carpet area provides main financial support for contemporary art and even in the absence of the government's expected support, the Indian art market has made its mark on the world level. Growth rate is slow but fast developing India is attracting the attention of museums and private collectors around the world and the global appeal of Indian art is increasing rapidly. Due to the changing social, political and economic scenario of a developing country like India, a promising rise in art market can also be seen. It is being seen that the artworks of young artists are also being sold, and art activities are expanding, which is a sign of the natural progress of any growing market.

Now it is necessary to mention here that we have only been discussing and discussing for a long time by making an insistence on the market by making an insistence, But the fact is that the market is also our need, just to see that we should not be left in the market as a puppet. The artist also needs regular money so that he can give his creativity a direction uninterrupted, enriched. In the

absence of material, do not let your art die by trapping in other junkies of other personal needs. But it is not fair to work on market demand. This product is like selling flat, car, TV, fridge, dining table.

Indian art came to headlines around the world, when painter Tyeb Mehta's painting sold for one and a half million rupees in New York's Christie's Gallery, the most expensive Indian painting ever made. This market has made many excuses. Saphron Art, a Mumbai-based art company from Mumbai, sold 140 artifacts' worth 13 crores through Internet auction, which is the biggest in Indian art history. Company President Dinesh Vazirani says that there has been a lot of change in the thinking of the Indian people before they used to invest money only in gold. But today they are beginning to understand the value of art.

In addition, the art to its private consumption value, has been a more gainful investment than some fixed income securities and has performed nearly as well as stocks over the long term.

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